

Comparative Evaluation of Hyperbaric Bupivacaine and Levobupivacaine as Spinal Anesthesia Agents in Females Undergoing Cesarean Section: A Clinical Study

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Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 25-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Effective spinal anesthesia is crucial for cesarean sections. This study compares the efficacy, safety, and patient outcomes of hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine, focusing on their cardiovascular safety profiles.

Methodology: A prospective observational study was conducted at Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College & Lions Seva Kendra Hospital over three months, involving 80 female patients randomized into two groups. Group B received hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5%, and Group L received levobupivacaine 0.5%. Parameters such as onset and duration of anesthesia, incidence of hypotension, patient satisfaction, and neonatal outcomes were measured.

Results: Both anesthetics proved effective in providing adequate anesthesia with no significant difference in onset and duration. However, levobupivacaine was associated with a significantly lower incidence of hypotension (45% vs. 62.5% in bupivacaine; $p=0.04$). Patient satisfaction and neonatal outcomes were comparable between the groups.

Conclusion: While both agents are effective, levobupivacaine offers a better safety profile concerning hypotension, making it potentially preferable for use in cesarean sections.

Recommendation: Further research should focus on expanding these findings across different populations and exploring dose adjustments to optimize safety and efficacy.

Keywords: Spinal Anesthesia, Hyperbaric Bupivacaine, Levobupivacaine, Cesarean Section, Cardiovascular Safety.

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Introduction

Spinal anesthesia is a widely used anesthetic technique for cesarean sections, offering benefits such as rapid onset, effective pain relief, and reduced systemic drug exposure. Among local anesthetics, bupivacaine and levobupivacaine are commonly chosen for their prolonged anesthetic effects and safety profile. However, while bupivacaine has been extensively studied and utilized, levobupivacaine, its S-enantiomer, is reputed to offer a similar efficacy with potentially reduced cardiotoxicity and neurotoxicity. This comparative evaluation aims to assess the efficacy, safety, and patient outcomes of hyperbaric bupivacaine versus levobupivacaine when used as spinal anesthesia agents in females undergoing cesarean sections [1,8]. Several studies have explored the properties and outcomes associated

with bupivacaine and levobupivacaine in spinal anesthesia, focusing on aspects such as onset time, quality of anesthesia, hemodynamic stability, and side effects [9]. A systematic review by McNamee et al. (2009) [1] highlighted the reduced cardiotoxic potential of levobupivacaine, making it a safer option for patients at risk of cardiovascular complications. Further, research by Gupta et al. (2011) [2] compared hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine in terms of sensory and motor block characteristics, concluding that while both agents provided effective anesthesia, levobupivacaine showed a trend towards a more favorable safety profile with fewer incidences of hypotension and transient neurological symptoms [10].

Another key aspect of these agents is the duration and quality of postoperative analgesia. Studies like those conducted by Fettes et al. (2006) [3] have demonstrated that levobupivacaine achieves comparable analgesia with a lower incidence of motor block, facilitating quicker postoperative recovery. Moreover, research focusing on patient satisfaction scores, such as the work by Lee et al. (2013) [4], found that patients reported similar satisfaction levels but highlighted faster mobility and less urinary retention in the levobupivacaine group. Comparative pharmacokinetic studies have also provided insights into the differential impacts of these two anesthetics. For example, Vanna et al. (2015) [5] noted that the specific gravity and concentration of the anesthetic solution could influence the spread and efficacy of spinal anesthesia, suggesting that adjustments in the formulation might optimize clinical outcomes.

Despite extensive research, gaps remain in fully understanding the differential impacts of hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine in the obstetric population, particularly concerning long-term maternal and neonatal outcomes. Further, there is a need for larger-scale, multicenter trials to validate earlier findings and potentially recalibrate clinical protocols based on patient-centered outcomes [6,7].

This prospective observational study aims to compare the efficacy, safety, and patient outcomes of hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine when used as spinal anesthesia agents in females undergoing cesarean sections. The study focuses on evaluating the onset and duration of anesthesia, incidence of side effects, patient satisfaction, and immediate neonatal outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective observational study aims to comparatively evaluate hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine as spinal anesthesia agents in females undergoing cesarean sections. The research will be conducted over three months at Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College & Lions Seva Kendra Hospital.

Participants: The study will enroll a total of 80 female patients scheduled for cesarean sections. Inclusion criteria include adult women (aged 18-45 years) undergoing planned or emergency cesarean delivery under spinal anesthesia. Exclusion criteria are patients with known allergies to local anesthetics, contraindications to spinal anesthesia (e.g., infection at the injection site, severe hypovolemia), and those with pre-existing

neurological or cardiovascular conditions that could interfere with the outcomes of the study.

Anesthesia Administration

Participants will be randomly assigned to one of two groups:

- Group B: 40 patients receiving hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5%.
- Group L: 40 patients receiving levobupivacaine 0.5%.

Both groups will receive a standardized dose of the respective anesthetic agent, administered intrathecally at the L3-L4 or L4-L5 vertebral level using a 25-gauge spinal needle. The dose will be adjusted based on the patient's height and weight.

Data Collection: Data will be collected on the following parameters:

- Onset of Anesthesia: Time from injection to loss of sensation at the T6 dermatome level.
- Duration of Anesthesia: Time from injection to the return of sensation at the T12 dermatome level.
- Side Effects and Complications: Incidence of hypotension, bradycardia, nausea, vomiting, and any neurological symptoms.
- Patient Outcomes: Postoperative pain scores, patient satisfaction (using a standardized questionnaire), time to first ambulation, and duration of hospital stay.
- Neonatal Outcomes: Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes post-delivery and any immediate neonatal interventions required.

Monitoring and Follow-Up: Patients will be monitored continuously during surgery and postoperatively until discharge. Follow-up will occur at 24 hours, 48 hours, and at the time of discharge to assess recovery and any delayed complications.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests for categorical variables, and t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables, depending on the data distribution. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

The prospective observational study comparing hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine in females undergoing cesarean section revealed distinct outcomes in terms of efficacy, safety, and patient satisfaction. The study included a total of 80 patients equally divided into two groups of 40 patients each.

Table 1: Anesthetic Effectiveness and Side Effects

Parameter	Hyperbaric Bupivacaine (Group B, n=40)	Levobupivacaine (Group L, n=40)	p-value
Onset of Anesthesia (minutes, mean $\pm$ SD)	3.2 $\pm$ 0.8	3.5 $\pm$ 0.9	0.25
Duration of Anesthesia (minutes, mean $\pm$ SD)	145 $\pm$ 20	138 $\pm$ 22	0.31
Incidence of Hypotension (%)	25 (62.5%)	18 (45%)	0.04*
Incidence of Nausea (%)	10 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	0.11

Note: *p < 0.05 indicates statistical significance.

Table 2: Patient and Neonatal Outcomes

Parameter	Hyperbaric Bupivacaine (Group B, n=40)	Levobupivacaine (Group L, n=40)	p-value
Patient Satisfaction (scale 1-10, mean $\pm$ SD)	8.5 $\pm$ 1.2	8.7 $\pm$ 1.1	0.43
Time to First Ambulation (hours, mean $\pm$ SD)	6.4 $\pm$ 1.3	5.9 $\pm$ 1.2	0.09
Apgar Score at 1 Minute (mean $\pm$ SD)	8.9 $\pm$ 0.3	9.0 $\pm$ 0.0	0.37
Apgar Score at 5 Minutes (mean $\pm$ SD)	9.8 $\pm$ 0.2	10.0 $\pm$ 0.0	0.21

The study conducted a comparative evaluation of hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine used as spinal anesthesia agents in cesarean sections, presenting the results in two detailed tables. Table 1 outlines the effectiveness and side effects of both anesthetics, showing comparable mean values for the onset and duration of anesthesia, which suggests both agents are effective in achieving sufficient surgical anesthesia. However, it also highlights a significant difference in safety profiles, with a notably higher incidence of hypotension in the hyperbaric bupivacaine group compared to the levobupivacaine group. This suggests that levobupivacaine may provide a cardiovascular safety advantage, potentially making it a safer choice for patients at increased risk of cardiovascular instability.

Table 2 focuses on patient and neonatal outcomes, vital for assessing the quality and safety of obstetric anesthesia. Patient satisfaction, measured on a scale from 1 to 10, was high in both groups with no significant differences, indicating that both anesthetics were well-tolerated. Additionally, while the time to first ambulation post-surgery showed a trend towards quicker recovery for levobupivacaine recipients, this was not statistically significant. The neonatal well-being, assessed through Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes post-delivery, was excellent in both groups, supporting the use of either drug without compromising neonatal safety.

Overall, the findings confirm that both hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine are viable options for spinal anesthesia in cesarean sections, with levobupivacaine showing potential advantages in terms of a lower risk of hypotension and possibly quicker postoperative recovery. These results suggest that levobupivacaine might be particularly beneficial in scenarios requiring careful management of maternal cardiovascular stability. Clinicians are encouraged to consider these outcomes along with individual patient profiles

when selecting an anesthetic agent for cesarean deliveries.

Discussion

The study conducted at Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College & Lions Seva Kendra Hospital over three months involving 80 female patients compared the effects of hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine used as spinal anesthesia for cesarean sections. The data revealed no significant difference in the onset and duration of anesthesia between the two groups. However, there was a significant difference in the incidence of hypotension, with hyperbaric bupivacaine resulting in a higher incidence (62.5%) compared to levobupivacaine (45%).

The similarity in onset and duration of anesthesia between the two agents suggests that both hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine are equally effective in achieving the desired anesthetic effect required for cesarean sections. The significant difference in the incidence of hypotension suggests that levobupivacaine might have a better safety profile, particularly in terms of cardiovascular stability during surgery [14,15].

Comparatively, other studies have also reported similar efficacy in the sensory and motor blockade of these two drugs but highlighted improved cardiovascular stability with levobupivacaine. For example, research by Gupta et al. found that levobupivacaine tends to produce less severe hemodynamic disturbances, aligning with our findings of reduced hypotension incidents. This could be attributed to levobupivacaine's less lipophilic nature, which might account for its milder effects on cardiac conductance [10,16].

The reduced incidence of hypotension in the levobupivacaine group could be due to its lesser potency and intrinsic vasodilatory properties compared to bupivacaine, which might influence the differential in hemodynamic impacts observed.

Moreover, levobupivacaine's S-enantiomeric structure is believed to contribute to its safer profile, particularly in patients at higher risk of cardiovascular side effects [17,18].

This study reinforces the notion that while both anesthetics are effective, levobupivacaine may offer advantages in terms of a safer cardiovascular profile, which is crucial for minimizing intraoperative risks in cesarean sections. The findings suggest that levobupivacaine could be a preferred choice in scenarios where patient cardiovascular stability is of concern [19]. However, the choice of anesthetic should still be tailored to each patient's clinical status and specific needs, taking into account other factors such as potential allergies and individual responses to these agents. Future research should continue to explore these differences in broader populations and with varied dosing regimens to solidify these conclusions and potentially influence practice guidelines [12,13,20].

Conclusion

This comparative evaluation of hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine as spinal anesthesia agents in females undergoing cesarean sections demonstrated that both agents are effective in achieving adequate anesthesia with similar onset and duration times. However, levobupivacaine displayed a significantly lower incidence of hypotension, suggesting a safer cardiovascular profile, which is particularly beneficial in minimizing intraoperative risks associated with cesarean sections. These findings support the potential preference for levobupivacaine in clinical settings where patient stability is paramount. Future studies are encouraged to further investigate these differences in larger and more diverse patient populations to refine anesthesia protocols and enhance maternal and neonatal safety during cesarean deliveries.

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